

Paper 13

**A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON COMPARISONS OF
STOCK PRICES PREVAILING IN THE CASH
MARKET AND FUTURES MARKET WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO BANKS**

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Abstract:

In this current era of the 21st century, the economic scenario of our nation has taken altogether a 360 degree turn. Many companies such as Infosys, ITC, TATA, Reliance, etc have established themselves in the national as well as international market. Most of the Indians have come up with various start-ups. This has altogether contributed in the improvement of the economic conditions of our country.

Through the growth of various industries and sectors, many people have started to invest their earnings in various companies of different industries, namely, the banking industry, the pharmaceutical industry, the textile industry, the steel industry, the automobile industry and many more, with an expectation to earn a high rate of return. The investors evaluate the best companies in which they can invest through NSE NIFTY and BSE SENSEX. Sensex is a figure which indicates the relative prices of shares and stocks of the companies listed under the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE). Nifty is a figure which indicates the relative prices of shares and stocks of the companies listed under the National Stock Exchange (NSE).

Derivatives are the products that derive their value on the basis of an underlying asset. The underlying asset can be a commodity, a currency or a security. Among the various types of derivatives, we are going to consider futures as the main highlight in our study. The main aim of our study will be to compare the share prices of various banks in the cash market and the futures market. The data that will be collected by us for our study will be secondary data and we will understand the changes in prices of the cash market and futures market through trends.

Keywords: companies, prices, derivatives, market, industry, stock, shares, banks.

1.INTRODUCTION:

With the development of Systematic Investment Plans (SIPs) and online investment, investment procedures have become easy for every investor. Investors invest in various avenues namely shares, stocks, debentures, gold bonds, mutual funds, commodities and so on. People invest in the shares of various companies which are listed under the

National Stock Exchange (NSE) and the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE). The concept of sensex and nifty serves as a guide to evaluate the companies where an investor can invest. The increase and decrease in the share prices are evaluated by the demand and supply for the shares.

Derivatives are mainly based on the prices at a future date if we enter in a contract today. The type of derivative we are mainly going to focus in our study is futures. We are going to compare the prices under the cash market and futures market of six Indian banks.

2. OBJECTIVES:

- To analyse the changes in the prices prevailing in the cash market and futures market of some banks of India.
- To compare the prices under the cash market and the futures market.
- To evaluate the changes in the trading volumes under the cash market.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Sl. No.	Title	Researcher(s)	Year	Summary
1.	The importance of the financial derivatives markets to economic development in the world's four major economies.	Duc Hong Vo, Son Van Huynh, Anh The Vo and Dao Thi-Thieu Ha.	February 2019	In this paper, the researchers have investigated the dynamic relationship between the derivatives markets and economic development of the 4 large economies, i.e., CIJU (China, India, Japan and the US). They made use of Granger-casuality test in the framework of vector error correction model (VECM) to examine this casual and dynamic relation with data for the period 1998 to 2017. They concluded that development of the derivatives markets had a positive effect on economic growth in the short run, as indicated in India, Japan and the US, although it may gradually turn negative, as in China.
2.	Performance of	Shaik Masood.	September	This study mainly deals

	commodity derivatives market in India: An analytical study.		2018	with commodity derivatives trading which has become indispensable in the hyper competitive era created by globalization and open market economies.
3.	The role of over-the-counter (OTC) derivatives in global financial crisis and corporate failures in recent times and its regulatory impacts.	Dr. Issahaku Salifu (FCCA).	November 2018	This paper deals with the role played by over-the-counter derivatives in the recent global financial crisis and corporate failures, and the extent to which these have impacted the regulation of OTC derivatives products and markets. This study has shown that the global financial crisis that brought world economies to recession indicated that there was a combination of factors that were responsible for this unfortunate economic meltdown.
4.	The impact of the use of financial derivatives on Chinese listed banks.	Rui Deng, Qiutong Ye, Wenrui Zhang and Si Chen.	November 2018	Based on the research on the main users of financial derivatives, commercial banks, using data of 16 listed commercial banks in China from 2012 to 2017, this paper finds that the fair value of financial derivatives of commercial banks is negatively correlated with the risk level.
5.	Next level risk management? Hedging and trading strategies of volatile derivatives using VIX futures.	Ernst J Fahling, Elmar Steurer, Tobias Schadler and Adrian Volz.	December 2018	This paper analyses how volatility derivatives on the volatility index VIX can be used as trading and risk management tools for investors and traders. This paper shows how VIX

				futures and options can hedge equity portfolios and when they are superior to traditional hedging alternative and compares the outcome of a VIX hedging strategy with a Buy and Hold strategy of the S and P 500 index over a time period of 20 years.
6.	Qualitative risk coverage in agriculture through derivative financial instruments based on Selyaninov indices.	Cristian Kevorchian, Camelia Gavrilesu and Gheorghe Hurduzeu	2013	This paper concludes that risk coverage in the case of certain weather phenomena with low risk but high occurrence probability is a necessity that can reduce the negative impact at farm economy level. The weather derivatives market requires certain adjustments in the sense of unifying the price establishment methodologies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The data collection process was purely based on secondary data. We obtained the secondary data from the websites. We studied the changes in the share prices under the cash market and futures market of six Indian banks by understanding the trend of the movements, whether it was upward or downward.

4.DATA ANALYSIS:

1. HDFC BANK:

About:

- In 1994, HDFC Bank was incorporated with its registered office in Mumbai, Maharashtra.
- Its first corporate office and a full service branch at Sandoz house, Worli were inaugurated by then union finance minister, Manmohan Singh.
- It was founded in august 1994.
- The area served by HDFC Bank is India.

- HDFC bank comes under the banking and financial services industry.
- BSE: 500180
- NSE: HDFCBANK
- NYSE: HDB
- BSE SENSEX Constituent
- CNX Nifty Constituent
- Non exe chairperson of HDFC Bank Shyamala Gopinath.
- Managing director of HDFC Bank is Aditya Puri.
- HDFC Bank deals with products such as credit cards, consumer banking, banking, finance and insurance, investment banking, mortgage loans, private banking, private equity, wealth management.

NSE NIFTY of HDFC Bank:

CASH MARKET					NSE NIFTY OF HDFC BANK LTD FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 22ND JULY 2019			FUTURES MARKET
Date	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Volume	Expiry Date	Close Price	Percentage Change	
09/07/2019	2379	31↓	-1.29%	4,120,672	29/08/2019	2401	-1.35%	
10/07/2019	2389	10↑	0.42%	2,892,287	29/08/2019	2406	0.20%	
11/07/2019	2407	18↑	0.75%	2,274,399	29/08/2019	2421	0.62%	
12/07/2019	2394	13↓	-0.54%	2,244,068	29/08/2019	2410	-0.48%	
15/07/2019	2395	1↑	0.04%	2,058,296	29/08/2019	2411	0.08%	
16/07/2019	2391	4↓	-0.17%	3,192,642	29/08/2019	2398	-0.55%	
17/07/2019	2397	6↑	0.25%	1,939,934	29/08/2019	2400	0.07%	
18/07/2019	2412	15↑	0.63%	2,700,646	29/08/2019	2414	0.59%	
19/07/2019	2376	36↓	-1.49%	2,234,807	29/08/2019	2377	-1.52%	
22/07/2019	2297	79↓	-3.44%	5,542,824	29/08/2019	2311	-2.78%	

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.92%
10/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.71%
11/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.58%
12/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.67%
15/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.67%
16/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.29%
17/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.13%

18/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.08%
19/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.04%
22/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.61%

2. STATE BANK OF INDIA (SBI):

About:

- State Bank of India is an Indian multinational public sector banking and financial services statutory body.
- Its headquarters are in Mumbai, Maharashtra.
- It is ranked 216th in fortune global 500 list of world's biggest corporations as of 2018.
- The tagline for this bank is **the banker to every Indian**.
- NSE: SBIN
- BSE: 500112
- LSE: SBID
- BSE SENSEX Constituent
- CNX Nifty Constituent
- SBI comes under the banking and financial services industry.
- It was founded in 2/6/1806 as bank of Calcutta and was named as State Bank of India on 1/7/1955.
- The chairman of SBI is Rajnish Kumar
- The products SBI deals with are retail banking, corporate banking, investment banking, mortgage loans, private banking, wealth management, credit cards, finance and insurance.

NSE NIFTY of SBI:

NSE NIFTY OF STATE BANK OF INDIA FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 2ND JULY 2019							
CASH MARKET				FUTURE MARKET			
Date	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Volume	Expiry Date	Close Price	Percentage Change
09/07/2019	360	5↑	1.41%	16,579,914	29/08/2019	363	1.05%
10/07/2019	354	6↓	-1.67%	18,681,819	29/08/2019	357	-1.53%
11/07/2019	363	9↑	2.54%	20,048,321	29/08/2019	365	2.23%
12/07/2019	364	1↑	0.28%	14,661,748	29/08/2019	366	0.22%
15/07/2019	360	4↓	-1.09%	15,665,939	29/08/2019	361	-1.05%
16/07/2019	364	4↑	1.11%	16,251,836	29/08/2019	366	1.11%
17/07/2019	372	8↑	2.19%	17,545,177	29/08/2019	374	2.16%
18/07/2019	364	8↓	-2.15%	21,691,056	29/08/2019	367	-1.94%
19/07/2019	356	8↓	-2.19%	22,213,173	29/08/2019	359	-2.14%
22/07/2019	351	5↓	-1.40%	19,682,038	29/08/2019	354	-1.38%

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.83%
10/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.85%
11/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.55%
12/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.55%
15/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.28%
16/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.55%
17/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.54%
18/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.82%
19/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.84%
22/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.85%

3. KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK:**About:**

- Kotak Mahindra Bank is an Indian private sector bank.
- The headquarters are situated in Mumbai, Maharashtra.
- It was founded in February 2003.
- BSE: 500247
- NSE: KOTAKBANK
- CNX Nifty Constituent
- It was founded by Uday Kotak.
- The chairman of Kotak Mahindra Bank is Prakash Apte.
- The MD and CEO is Uday Kotak.
- It comes under the banking and financial services industry.
- It offers banking products for corporate and retail customers.

NSE NIFTY of Kotak Mahindra Bank:

NSE NIFTY OF KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK LTD FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 22ND JULY 2019

Date	CASH MARKET				FUTURES MARKET		
	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Volume	Expiry Date	Close Price	Percentage Change
09/07/2019	1463	12↓	-0.81%	2,297,420	29/08/2019	1470	-0.98%
10/07/2019	1476	13↑	0.89%	2,180,732	29/08/2019	1481	0.80%
11/07/2019	1485	9↑	0.61%	1,598,491	29/08/2019	1488	0.42%
12/07/2019	1484	1↓	-0.07%	2,072,545	29/08/2019	1489	0.11%
15/07/2019	1508	24↑	1.62%	1,752,154	29/08/2019	1509	1.33%
16/07/2019	1501	7↓	-0.46%	1,351,435	29/08/2019	1504	-0.35%
17/07/2019	1535	34↑	2.27%	6,202,534	29/08/2019	1534	1.99%
18/07/2019	1538	3↑	0.20%	2,266,820	29/08/2019	1540	0.41%
19/07/2019	1499	39↓	-2.54%	2,094,229	29/08/2019	1501	-2.57%
22/07/2019	1454	45↓	-3%	3,423,157	29/08/2019	1463	-2.52%

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.48%
10/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.34%
11/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.20%
12/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.34%
15/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.07%
16/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.20%
17/7/2019	29/8/2019	Downward	-0.07%
18/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.13%
19/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.13%
22/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.62%

4. INDUSIND BANK:**About:**

- IndusInd bank ltd is a Mumbai based Indian new generation bank, established in 1994.
- The bank offers commercial, transactional and electronic banking products and services.
- NSE: INDUSINDBK
- BSE:532187
- CNX Nifty Constituent
- IndusInd bank was inaugurated in April 1994 by then union finance minister Manmohan Singh.

- IndusInd bank is the first among the new generation private banks in India.

NSE NIFTY of IndusInd Bank:

CASH MARKET					NSE NIFTY OF INDUSIND BANK LTD FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 22ND 2019				FUTURE MARKET		
Date	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Volume	Expiry Date	Close Price	Percentage Change				
09/07/2019	1492	15↑	1.02%	3,733,488	29/08/2019	1502	1.18%				
10/07/2019	1487	05↓	-0.34%	3,222,571	29/08/2019	1492	-0.69%				
11/07/2019	1541	54↑	3.63%	4,337,246	29/08/2019	1543	3.48%				
12/07/2019	1510	31↓	-2.01%	10,637,123	29/08/2019	1515	-1.86%				
15/07/2019	1475	35↓	-2.32%	5,656,516	29/08/2019	1481	-2.24%				
16/07/2019	1473	02↓	-0.14%	3,863,867	29/08/2019	1479	-0.11%				
17/07/2019	1501	28↑	1.90%	5,290,039	29/08/2019	1505	1.78%				
18/07/2019	1471	30↓	-1.99%	2,404,071	29/08/2019	1476	-1.93%				
19/07/2019	1422	49↓	-3.33%	4,698,852	29/08/2019	1422	-3.69%				
22/07/2019	1418	04↓	-0.28%	4,578,591	29/08/2019	1411	-0.04%				

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.67%
10/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.34%
11/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.13%
12/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.33%
15/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.41%
16/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.41%
17/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.27%
18/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.34%
19/7/2019	29/8/2019	Equal	0%
22/7/2019	29/8/2019	Downward	-0.49%

5. YES BANK:

About:

- Yes bank was founded by Rana Kapoor and Ashok Kapoor.
- It was founded in 2004.
- It is headquartered in Mumbai, Maharashtra.
- Yes bank belongs to the banking and financial services industry.
- BSE: 532648
- NSE: YESBANK
- The chairman is Brahm Dutt.
- The MD and CEO is Ravneet Gill.

- Yes bank deals with products such as credit cards, consumer banking, corporate banking, finance and insurance, mortgage loans, private banking, wealth management, investment banking.
- Derives most of its revenues through arranging syndicated loans and through corporate banking.
- It has a strategic partnership with us government based OPIC and with Wells Fargo.

NSE NIFTY of Yes Bank:

NSE NIFTY OF YES BANK LTD FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 22ND JULY 2019								
Date	CASH MARKET				Volume	FUTURES MARKET		
	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Expiry Date		Close Price	Percentage Change	
09/07/2019	91	2↓	-2.15%	137,863,884	29/08/2019	92	-2.07%	
10/07/2019	93	2↑	2.20%	75,776,545	29/08/2019	94	1.79%	
11/07/2019	92	1↓	-1.08%	73,432,269	29/08/2019	93	-0.43%	
12/07/2019	94	2↑	2.17%	60,702,978	29/08/2019	95	1.87%	
15/07/2019	93	1↓	-1.06%	126,736,904	29/08/2019	94	-1.16%	
16/07/2019	104	11↑	11.83%	228,682,135	29/08/2019	105	11.81%	
17/07/2019	98	6↓	-6.12%	238,375,009	29/08/2019	99	-5.76%	
18/07/2019	86	12↓	-12.24%	229,258,092	29/08/2019	86	-12.87%	
19/07/2019	83	3↓	-3.49%	145,863,654	29/08/2019	84	-3.01%	
22/07/2019	91	8↑	9.64%	208,758,719	29/08/2019	92	9.68%	

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.10%
10/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.08%
11/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.09%
12/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.06%
15/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.08%
16/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.96%
17/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.02%
18/7/2019	29/8/2019	Equal	0%
19/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.20%
22/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.10%

6. BANK OF BARODA(BOB):

About:

- Bank of Baroda is an Indian Multinational public sector banking and financial services company.
- It is owned by the Government of India.
- It is the second largest public sector bank in India.
- BSE: 532134
- NSE: BANKBARODA
- CNX Nifty Constituent
- It was founded on 20th July 1908.
- It was founded by Sayajirao Gaekwad.
- Its headquarters are situated in Vadodara, Gujarat.
- It serves India and countries worldwide.
- The chairman of BOB is Hasmukh Adhia.
- The MD and CEO is P.S. Jayakumar.
- The products and services it deals with are consumer banking, corporate banking, finance and insurance, investment banking, mortgage loans, private equity, savings, securities, asset management and wealth management.
- Based on 2019 data, it is ranked 1145 on Forbes Global 2000 list.

NSE NIFTY of Bank of Baroda:

NSE NIFTY OF BANK OF BARODA LTD FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 22ND JULY 2019								
CASH MARKET					FUTURE MARKET			
Date	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Volume	Expiry Date	Close Price	Percentage Change	
09/07/2019	126	1↑	0.80%	14,869,226	29/08/2019	127	1.28%	
10/07/2019	124	2↓	-1.59%	15,786,409	29/08/2019	125	-1.38%	
11/07/2019	126	2↑	1.61%	14,450,972	29/08/2019	127	1.80%	
12/07/2019	126	0	0.00%	12,403,617	29/08/2019	127	-0.16%	
15/07/2019	122	4↓	-3.17%	15,285,529	29/08/2019	123	-3.31%	
16/07/2019	124	2↑	1.64%	19,467,661	29/08/2019	125	1.83%	
17/07/2019	127	3↑	2.42%	17,922,297	29/08/2019	128	2.24%	
18/07/2019	121	6↓	-4.72%	21,215,697	29/08/2019	122	-4.42%	
19/07/2019	118	3↓	-2.48%	19,834,528	29/08/2019	119	-3.03%	
22/07/2019	118	0	0.00%	18,668,714	29/08/2019	119	0.63%	

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.79%
10/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.81%
11/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.79%
12/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.79%
15/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.82%
16/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.81%
17/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.79%
18/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.83%
19/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.85%
22/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.85%

FINDINGS:

- We found many upward trends while comparing the changes in prices under the cash market and futures market.
- The exceptions were :
Kotak Mahindra Bank – 17th July 2019
IndusInd Bank – 19th July 2019 and 22nd July 2019
Yes Bank – 18th July 2019
- Under the cash market of HDFC Bank, we can find a drastic decrease in the value of share price on 22nd July 2019; 79 decrease. The peak level of the trading volume of HDFC Bank was 5,542,824 on 22nd July 2019 and the trough level was 1,939,934 on 17th July 2019.
- We can find a good increase in the share price of SBI on 11th July 2019; 9 increase. There was continuous decrease in the share prices during the three days at the end of the window period. The peak level of the trading volume of SBI was 22,213,173 on 19th July 2019 and the trough level was 14,661,748 on 12th July 2019.
- Kotak Mahindra Bank has faced a drastic decrease of its share price on 22nd July 2019; 45 decrease. The peak level of the trading volume of Kotak Mahindra Bank was 6,202,534 on 17th July 2019 and the trough level was 1,351,435 on 16th July 2019.
- IndusInd Bank has experienced an increase in its share price on 11th July 2019; 54 increase and has faced a drastic decrease on 19th July 2019; 49 decrease. The peak level of the trading volume of IndusInd Bank was 10,637,123 on 12th July 2019 and the trough level was 2,404,071 on 18th July 2019.
- Yes bank has faced a drastic decrease in its share price on 18th July 2019; 12 decrease. The peak level of the trading volume of Yes Bank was 238,375,009 on 17th July 2019 and the trough level was 60,702,978 on 12th July 2019.
- Bank of Baroda has faced a decrease in its share price on 18th July 2019; 6 decrease. The peak level of the trading volume of Bank of Baroda was 21,215,697 on 18th July 2019 and the trough level was 12,403,617 on 12th July 2019.

CONCLUSION:

By the whole study, we can conclude that the futures market seem to be much more profitable as compared to the cash market because the share prices under the futures market are comparatively higher. During the window period of 10 days, i.e 9th July 2019 – 22nd July 2019, investing in the futures market would seem as a feasible option for the investors.

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